

CORRELATING STUDENTS' PERSONALITY TYPES WITH CURRICULUM EXITS IN PALIPARAN III SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

Francis E. Factura¹, Reynaldo F. Dinampo² and Julius B. Paleracio¹

¹ *Paliparan III Senior High School, City of Dasmariñas, Cavite, Philippines*
² *Dr. Jose P. Rizal Senior High School, City of Dasmariñas, Cavite, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the correlation between student personality types and curriculum exits of selected 12th-grade senior high school graduates from Paliparan III Senior High School, City of Dasmariñas, Cavite. The variables treated for their relationship were the RIASEC personality types of the students and their preferred majors. Respondents were 502 students, including 256 males and 246 females. The descriptive correlative research design was used in the study. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to present the descriptive data. Chi-Square was used to determine the significant relationship between students' personality types and curriculum-resultant nominal data. The result of the statistical treatment used in this study yielded the following findings: Regarding the personality types, most of the students surveyed were Social with a total of 122 out of 502 students; One hundred seventeen (117) out of 502 students were Conventional; eighty-six (86) students were Realistic; seventy (70) students were Artistic; fifty-four (54) students were Investigative, and fifty-three (53) out of 502 students were Enterprising. On the other hand, the results showed that among the three hundred ninety-nine (399) out of 502 students would choose higher education or the "Kolehiyo" curriculum as their curriculum exit. These students believe that a college degree offers diverse employment opportunities and greater earning potential. Furthermore, the null hypothesis on the association between RIASEC personality types and SHS curriculum completions was rejected.

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd), led by former Secretary Armin Luistro, FSJ, introduced the K-to-12 program in 2011 and made kindergarten a prerequisite for basic education. In the 2012–2013 academic year, the Philippines introduced the K–12 Basic Education Program, which includes Kindergarten and 12 years of Basic Education. Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Act of 2013, added two years of Senior High School (SHS) to the high school curriculum to better prepare students for postsecondary education with entrepreneurship, employment, and the development of middle-level skills as their exit in secondary program. The term "curriculum exit" refers to the range of opportunities that high school graduates will have after completing their education. Before the K–12 program was implemented, the Department of Education recognized and acknowledged the possible issues.

To proactively address these concerns, the Department of Education introduced the Career Guidance Program (DO 41, s. 2015). Additionally, the Department of Education (DepEd) has issued a memo (OUA-09-0710-0236, s. 2019) titled "Guidelines on the Utilization of Senior High School Career Guidance Program Modules and Reporting System" following Rule V of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013.

Several factors need to be considered when choosing a curriculum deviation following senior high school. Some of these factors include the family's financial standing, the student's unique skills and interests, and any potential impact from peers, friends, and family members. The relationship between a student's personality type and the curriculum exit they choose should also be considered. Selecting the ideal path is comparable to selecting the ideal college course or curriculum exit. According to Wilhelm and Comgeys (2004), selecting the right course is an important and life-changing decision that can be influenced by several variables, such as academic performance, grading practices, and even personality types. The proverb "Birds of a feather flock together" (Holland, 1996) refers to how people frequently seek advice, consider their interests, or just make popular decisions. Additionally, choosing a professional path is crucial for seniors graduating from high school because it is a lifelong process that changes as a person develops (Georgia Professional Information Center, 2013).

With the help of their personality types and curriculum exit, Grade 12 Senior High School graduates will be helped by this study in choosing their professional routes. It also acts as a reference for picking college classes that complement their technological and intellectual "know-how". The study will also be helpful to guidance counselors who keep an eye on students' conduct, occupational inventories, and academic achievement. These counselors use programs to assist students in honing their abilities and selecting the right courses based on their qualifications. The study offers useful information for researchers and analysts as well, information that can be saved and utilized for comparisons in the future. Particularly in the context of adopting a Career Tracking Program for senior high school students, this data can highlight the strengths and

weaknesses of pupils. Administrators and Program Proponents/Focal Persons/Coordinators can create localized policy guidelines for Project: TSERA-E2E through the SHS Curriculum Exit Fair with the information provided by the study. This fair features events including career talks, job fairs, business enterprise simulations, and tech-voc fairs, all of which are meant to improve students' talents in the professional tracks they have chosen.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the correlation between students' personality types and their curriculum exit profile in the Senior High School (SHS) setting. The process of choosing a curriculum exit involves more than simply considering the available options; it also entails considering various factors related to each student's career, such as compatibility with their personalities. Holland's theory of Career and Personality types is relevant to selecting an appropriate Career Pathway. Based on this conceptual framework, this study focuses on "Correlating Student Personality Types with Curriculum Exits in Paliparan 3 Senior High School" for the G12 students for the School Year 2022-2023. The findings of this study will serve as initial inputs for the development of localized policy guidelines for the Project: TSERA-E2E program. Some Grade 12 students at this school encounter difficulties when it comes to choosing their curriculum exit after completing senior high school.

More specifically, the study aims to address the following research questions:

1. What is the learner's basic information in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Age
 - c. Track, Strand & Specialization
 - d. Economic Status
2. What are the personality types of Paliparan 3 SHS Grade 12 students based on the RIASEC test?
3. What is the SHS Curriculum Exit profile of Paliparan III Senior High School Grade 12 students for SY 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant relationship between students' personality types and the SHS curriculum exits?
5. What are the localized policy guidelines of PROJECT: TSERA E2E to enhance the SHS curriculum exit fair of Paliparan III SHS?

METHODOLOGY

The subjects of the study are the graduating G12 students of Paliparan III Senior High School of the City of Dasmariñas for the School Year 2022-2023. The school is located at Block 194, Phase V, Paliparan Site, Barangay Paliparan III, City of Dasmariñas, Cavite, Philippines. The study has participated by five hundred two (502) G12 students of Paliparan III Senior High School as the main respondents using stratified sampling. The result will represent the number of respondents based on a stratified sub-group sample size.

As soon as the validity and reliability of the research instruments were established, the following steps were taken into full consideration: (1) Request for Permission – A letter of permission to conduct a survey was secured from the Office of the School Head and the letter was approved last June 5, 2023; (2) Permission Presentation - With the assistance of the Class Advisers/Work Immersion Teachers, the survey questionnaires containing the learner’s basic information, the Modified RIASEC Personality Rating Scale and their SHS CURRICULUM EXITS were administered or conducted. Afterward, the questionnaires were collected from the students (teachers) after they answered them; (3) Coding and Tabulation –The data was encoded through MS Excel, and IBM-SPSS version 21 was utilized in processing the data; (4) Analysis and Interpretation – The results were analyzed and interpreted statistically. The instrument used in this study is the RIASEC Students’ Personality Test by Holland was downloaded. With the approval of the author/owner of such instrument was located at <http://Hawaii.edu./cte/contact.html>. The website address of the University of Hawaii of Manoa, Career and Technical Education Center. The instrument used in this study is the RIASEC Students’ Personality Test by Holland. However, the researchers undergo the process of modification of the six (6) Personality tests. The RIASEC Personality Test Rating Scale (Modified Scale) is a modification made by Dinampo, and Fatura (2023) to measure further the magnitude of each personality to be used in their schools. This modified version has 42 statements with 7 statements per personality which is randomly arranged. Modified version wherein in the survey statements are arranged according to each personality types. In this version, the scoring remains the same while the interpretation is modified in the following manner: 1- Not Evident; 2-Rarely Evident; 3- Evident; 4-Highly Evident.

Table 1. The Final Scoring Guide of RIASEC Personality Test. (Dinampo and Fatura, 2023 final version)

R	Score	I	Score	A	Score	S	Score	E	Score	C	Score
1		8		15		22		29		36	
2		9		16		23		30		37	
3		10		17		24		31		38	
4		11		18		25		32		39	
5		12		19		26		33		40	
6		13		20		27		34		41	
7		14		21		28		35		42	
TOTAL		TOTAL		TOTAL		TOTAL		TOTAL		TOTAL	

Range	Verbal Interpretation
23-28	Highly Evident
17-22	Evident
11-16	Rarely Evident
5-10	Not Evident

Code	Score	V. Interpretation
Realistic		
Investigative		
Artistic		
Social		
Enterprising		
Conventional		

Since the instrument is a localized modified version, the researchers sought the help of the School Administration, some Faculty Members, a Research Focal Person,

and Practice Teachers in Paliparan III Senior High School using a Validation Tool, (adopted from Awa, 20212). Part of the validation process is through the tool used by the institution and this research itself which is also instrumental to the said validity. Based on their evaluations, comments, and suggestions, the Modified version as well as validated Research Instruments will be served as the final copy of the Survey questionnaire consisting of the RIASEC Personality types and SHS curriculum exits including the Learner’s Basic Information that is also aligned with the Statement of the Problems (SOPs).

The statistical techniques used in the study are essential for scientific research. This will be used for planning and designing the research title and statements of the problems; collecting data and analyzing using MS Excel spreadsheets as well as the SPSS software program; drawing meaningful interpretations, and reporting research findings. In the data analysis, descriptive statistics were used such as Frequency, Percentage, and Chi-Square to correlate the RIASEC Students Personality with the SHS Curriculum Exits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine the relationship of students’ personality types to their chosen or preferred SHS curriculum exits. The following are the results of the data analysis conducted:

1. What is the learner’s basic information in terms of:

- a. Sex
- b. Age
- c. Track, Strand & Specialization
- d. Economic Status

Table 2. Learners’ basic information in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	256	51.0
Female	246	49.0
TOTAL	502	100

The subjects of the study were two five hundred two (502) Grade 12 senior high students composed of 256 males and 246 females of Paliparan III Senior High School. Based on the total enrolled students for the SY 2022-2023, we have 460 males and 436 females. This data is based on the Learner Information System (LIS) which provides an

online facility that provides for the registration of learners enrolled in schools run or licensed by the Department of Education in the Philippines. Further, it is the national registry of all learners in Basic Education. (Department of Education, 2020, Learner Information System, para. 2)

Further, Paliparan III is a barangay in the city of Dasmariñas, in the province of Cavite. Its population as determined by the 2020 Census was 72,945. This represented 10.37% of the total population of Dasmariñas. The household population of Paliparan III in the 2015 Census was 68,194 broken down into 15,247 households or an average of 4.47 members per household. In addition, according to the 2015 Census, the age group with the highest population in Paliparan III is 15 to 19, with 7,487 individuals. Conversely, the age group with the lowest population is 80 and over, with 199 individuals. (Phil Atlas, 2020)

Table 3. Learner’s basic information in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
17-18 years old	356	70.9
19-20 years old	122	24.3
21 years old and above	24	04.8
TOTAL	502	100

Table 3 shows that most of the respondents belong to the 17-18 years old bracket with 356 learners while 122 respondents are ages 19-20 years old and there are 24 respondents which considered adult learners since they are 21 years old and above. This means that the typical age of Grade 11 learners is 16 years old (17-18 years old) according to the US education system. The same also applies in the Philippines wherein the typical age of Grade 12 learners is also 17-18 years of age. (Formoso, C. (2016, May 1), *Primer: What you should know about the K to 12 senior high schools? Philippine Daily Inquirer*)

Table 4. Learner's basic information in terms of Track, Strand, and Specialization

Track, Strand, Specialization	Frequency	Percentage
ACAD-STEM	39	7.8
ACAD-HUMMS	80	15.9
ACAD-ABM	115	22.9
ACAD-GAS	54	10.8
TVL-Industrial Arts, EPAS	30	6.0
TVL-Industrial Arts, EIM	50	10.0
TVL-Info & Com Tech, CSS	54	10.8
TVL-Home Economics, CBF	65	12.9
TVL-Home Economics, BHW	15	3.0
TOTAL	502	100

Based on the population and sample, table 4 shows that the study was participated by five hundred two (**502**) G12 students of Paliparan III Senior High School as the main respondents. Using the formula: *Stratified Sub-Group Sample Size equal to Total Sample Size divided by the Total Population multiplied by the desired sample which is 500 (this was computed within 80-90% of the desired sample size to get a higher generalizability index.* The result will represent the number of respondents based on a stratified sub-group sample size. Generalizability index, can be defined as the application of research findings based on a sample to the whole population, it also means that the findings of one study are transferable to another similar situation. Generalizability and transferability of the research are two interrelated characteristics of research. (Scientific Reports, 2023)

Table 5. Learner's basic information in terms of Economic Status

Economic Status	Frequency	Percentage
Poor (below P10,957.00)	226	45.0
Low Income but not poor (P10,957.00 - 21,914.00)	178	35.5
Low Middle (P21,914.00 -43,828.00)	72	14.3
Middle Class (P43,828.00 -76,669.00)	22	4.4
Upper Middle (P76,669.00 -131,484.00)	3	0.6

Upper but not rich (P131,484.00 - 219,140.00)	1	0.2
Rich (P219,140.00 - and above)	0	0.0
TOTAL	502	100

Table 5 reveals that most of the students belong to poor families wherein 226 respondents declare that their average monthly family income is below P10,957.00. followed by 178 respondents who affirm that their economic status is Low income but not poor. Further, 72 respondents belong to the low middle, 22 respondents affirm they are under Upper-Class income, 3 from Upper Middle, and 1 from Upper but not rich respectively. According to the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), a Filipino family of five needs, an average of P12, 082.00 per month to meet their minimum basic food and non-food needs. The PIDS also presented to the Senate Finance Committee the economic standing of a Filipino family of five based on their monthly income. (Philippine Statistic Authority, 2023)

2. What is the personality type of Paliparan 3 SHS Grade 12 students based on the RIASEC test?

Personality types refer to a systematic understanding of human behavior or the totality of somebody's attitudes, interests, behavioral patterns, emotional responses, social roles, and other individual traits that endure over long periods.

Figure 1 below shows the summary of the personality of the students based on the Holland Codes or RIASEC.

Figure 1 shows the personality profile of the respondents. It reveals that eighty-six (86) or seventeen (17.13) percent of the respondents are realistic in terms of personality, fifty-four (54) or eleven (11) percent of the respondents are investigative, seventy (70) percent of the respondents are artistic, one hundred twenty-two (122) or twenty-four (24) percent of the respondents are social, fifty-three (53) or eleven (11) percent of the respondents are enterprising and one hundred seventeen (117) or twenty-three (23) percent of the respondents are conventional. It means that most respondents are social in terms of their personality.

3. What is the SHS Curriculum Exit profile of Paliparan III Senior High School Grade 12 students for SY 2022-2023?

Curriculum exit refers to the doors of numerous opportunities that you will move through after your exit in senior high school. In addition, curriculum exit refers to a student's mastery of a particular course or program. It is a standards-based sequence of planned experiences where students practice and achieve proficiency in content and applied learning skills. In the Philippines, the four curriculum exits for the Senior High School curriculum are higher education, middle-level skills development, entrepreneurship, and employment.

Figure 2 above shows the preferred curriculum exits of the respondents. It reveals that three hundred ninety-nine (399) or seventy-nine (79) percent of the respondents want to go to college, fifteen (15) or three (3) percent of the respondents want to have a business, ten (10) or two (2) percent of the respondents preferred to develop their middle-level skills and seventy-eight (78) or sixteen (16) percent of the respondents preferred to get a job after graduation.

A notable number of respondents wanted to take a college degree and very few wanted to enter the entrepreneurial world, more so with developing a middle-level skill.

According to Cabral and Abanto (2020), in their study on the awareness of students on the curriculum exits, found that students in senior high school are moderately aware of the four curriculum exits. In other words, most students may be unfamiliar with but not aware of the deeper context of such (e.g., benefits, risks, etc.)

The Philippine Business for Education (PBE) has launched a program known as First Future to train SHS graduates for employment with the help of the Department of Education (DepEd), the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority, the University of the Philippines Open University, and 14 companies and organizations. 797 participants benefitted from the program. The study found that among the SHS students interviewed from 18 schools, 75.4% still plan to pursue higher education, 10% plan to get a job, 13.7% want to study while working, and 0.9% are still undecided. The SHS graduates said they do not believe they are prepared for work and have no confidence when it comes to competing with college graduates, and few companies are open to hiring them. A separate study conducted by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) in 2020 also evaluated the first batch of SHS graduates, only 20% entered the workforce while more than 70% are still attending college.

4. Is there a significant relationship between students' personality types and the SHS Curriculum exits?

Table 6. Correlation Between Realistic Personality and Preferred Curriculum Exit

REALISTIC VS. CURRICULUM EXITS	HIGHLY EVIDENT		EVIDENT		RARELY EVIDENT		NOT EVIDENT		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Higher Education "Kolehiyo"	45	37.60	19	23.79	2	2.30	0	2.30	66
Entrepreneurship "Negosyo"	1	1.71	2	1.08	0	0.10	0	0.10	3
Middle level Skills Development	1	1.71	2	1.08	0	0.10	0	0.10	3
Employment "Trabaho"	2	7.98	8	5.05	1	0.49	3	0.49	14
TOTAL	49		31		3		3		86
χ^2 COMP= 26.91 χ^2 TAB= 16.919 DF= 9 SIGNIFICANT 0.05 LEVEL									

Table 6 reveals the Chi-Square correlation between the realistic personality of the respondents and their preferred curriculum exits. It shows that those who have a very

strong realistic personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 45 and an expected frequency of 37.60; those who have a strong realistic personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 19 and the expected frequency of 23.79; those who have a weak realistic personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 2 with the expected frequency of 2.30; while those who have very weak realistic personality and preferred college as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and 2.30 expected frequency.

On the other hand, those respondents who had a very strong realistic personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 1.71; those who had a strong realistic personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 1.08; those who have weak and very weak realistic personality got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.10 respectively.

Further, those respondents who were very strong in their realistic personality and chose middle-skill as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 1.71; those who had a strong realistic personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 1.08; those who have weak and very weak realistic personality got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.10 respectively.

Lastly, those respondents who had a very strong realistic personality and chose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 7.98; those who had a strong realistic personality and work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 8 and an expected frequency of 5.05; those who had a weak realistic personality and choose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 0.49; those who are very weak in terms of realistic personality got an observed frequency of 3 and an expected frequency of 0.49. Realistic personality types are often described as hands-on. They are detail-oriented and thrive on structure and order. Realistic personality types are often drawn to careers in fields such as construction, mechanics, or law enforcement. Some famous people who have a Realistic personality type include George Washington, Abraham Lincoln, Barack Obama, and Bill Clinton. Realistic personality types are often seen as natural leaders and are often respected for their level-headedness and ability to stay calm under pressure. They are typically both honest and reliable, which can be a rare combination in the world of politics. Realistic personality types often have a strong sense of duty and are passionate about serving their country and protecting rights.

Table 7. Correlation Between Investigative Personality and Preferred Curriculum Exit

INVESTIGATIVE VS. CURRICULUM EXITS	HIGHLY EVIDENT		EVIDENT		RARELY EVIDENT		NOT EVIDENT		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
<i>Higher Education "Kolehiyo"</i>	30	25.81	8	7.59	3	6.07	0	1.52	41
<i>Entrepreneurship "Negosyo"</i>	1	0.63	0	0.19	0	0.15	0	0.04	1
<i>Middle-level Skills Development</i>	0	0.63	1	0.19	0	0.15	0	0.04	1
<i>Employment "Trabaho"</i>	3	6.93	1	2.04	5	1.63	2	0.41	11
TOTAL	34		10		8		2		54
<p>x^2 COMP=24.52 x^2 TAB=16.919 DF= 9 SIGNIFICANT 0.05 LEVEL</p>									

Table 7 discloses the correlation between the investigative personality of the respondents and their preferred curriculum exits. It shows that those who have a very strong investigative personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 30 and an expected frequency of 25.81; those who have a strong investigative personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 8 and the expected frequency of 7.59; those who have a weak investigative personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 3 with the expected frequency of 6.07; while those who have very weak investigative personality and preferred college as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and 1.52 expected frequency.

On the other hand, those respondents who had a very strong investigative personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 0.63; those who had a strong, weak, and very weak investigative personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.19, 0.15 and 0.04 respectively.

Further, those respondents who are very strong, weak, and very weak in their investigative personality and choose middle-skill as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.63, 0.15, and 0.04 respectively; those who had a strong investigative personality and choose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 0.19. Lastly, those respondents who had a very strong investigative personality and chose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 3 and an expected frequency of 6.93; those who had a strong investigative personality and work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 2.04; those who have a weak investigative personality and choose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 5 and an expected frequency of 1.63; those who are very weak in terms of investigative personality got an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 0.41.

Notably, many of the respondents who choose college as their curriculum exit have a very strong and strong investigative personality. The decision to take the route of entrepreneurship, middle-skill development, and work is just an alternative route, and the influence of that decision is more on the side of those who are very strong and strong in terms of realistic personality.

Investigative personality types are the “Thinkers” because they like working with ideas and theories. They love exploring their thoughts and they enjoy building their knowledge to gather a deeper understanding of the world. Typically, Investigative types are analytical, logical, and data-driven. They are intellectual, and inquisitive, and tend to enjoy solving complex problems using mathematics and science.

Table 8. Correlation Between Artistic Personality and Preferred Curriculum Exit

ARTISTIC VS. CURRICULUM EXITS	HIGHLY EVIDENT		EVIDENT		NOT EVIDENT		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Higher Education “Kolehiyo”	43	38.27	14	13.84	0	4.89	57
Entrepreneurship “Negosyo”	2	2.01	1	0.73	0	0.26	3
Employment “Trabaho”	2	6.71	2	2.43	6	0.86	10
TOTAL	47		17		6		70
x^2 COMP=39.69	x^2 TAB=9.488		SIGNIFICANT		DF=4		0.05 LEVEL

Table 8 shows the Chi-Square correlation between the artistic personality of the respondents and their preferred curriculum exits. It shows that those who have a very strong artistic personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 43 and an expected frequency of 38.27; those who have a strong artistic

personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 14 and the expected frequency of 13.84; those who have a very weak artistic personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency with the expected frequency of 4.89.

On the other hand, those respondents who had a very strong artistic personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 2.01; those who had a strong artistic personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 0.73; those respondents who have a very weak artistic personality got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.26.

Further, nobody among the respondents who has an artistic personality has chosen middle-skill development as their curriculum exit. And there is no recorded evidence for weak artistic personality types vis a vis to the curriculum exit.

Lastly, those respondents who had a very strong artistic personality and chose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 6.71; those who had a strong artistic personality and work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 2.43; those who are very weak in terms of artistic personality got an observed frequency of 6 and an expected frequency of 0.86.

Notably, most of the respondents who choose college as their curriculum exit have a very strong and strong artistic personality. The decision to take the route of middle-skill development and work is just an alternative route and influential to that decision is more on the side of those who are very strong and strong in terms of artistic personality. Nobody among the respondents has chosen entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit.

Artistic personality types are creative and expressive people. They like to think outside the box and are often inspired by their imagination. In general, they are sensitive and emotional which leads them to be passionate about their work. While they may not always be outgoing people, they usually have a strong appreciation for art, music, or other forms of self-expression such as craftspersons, sculptors, and weavers.

Table 9. Correlation Between Social Personality and Preferred Curriculum Exit

SOCIAL VS. CURRICULUM EXITS	HIGHLY EVIDENT		EVIDENT		RARELY EVIDENT		NOT EVIDENT		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Higher Educ "Kolehiyo"	71	64.89	20	20.14	0	0.75	0	5.22	91
Entrepreneurship "Negosyo"	4	3.57	1	1.11	0	0.04	0	0.29	5
Middle-level Skills Development	3	3.57	1	1.11	1	0.04	0	0.29	5
Employment "Trabaho"	9	14.98	5	4.65	0	0.17	7	1.20	21
TOTAL	87		27		1		7		122

χ^2 TAB = 16.919

χ^2 COMP = 30.14

DF – 9

SIGNIFICANT

0.05 LEVEL

Table 9 reveals the Chi-Square correlation between the social personality of the respondents and their preferred curriculum exits. It shows that those who have a very strong social personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 71 and an expected frequency of 64.89; those who have a strong social personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 20 and the expected frequency of 20.14; those who have a weak and very weak social personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.75, and 5.22 respectively.

On the other hand, those respondents who had a very strong social personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 4 and an expected frequency of 3.57; those who had a strong social personality and chose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 1.11; those who have a weak and very weak social personality and choose entrepreneurship as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.04, and 0.29 respectively. Further, those respondents who had very strong social personality and chose middle-level as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 3 and an expected frequency of 3.57; those who had a strong social personality and chose middle-level as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 1 and the expected frequency of 1.11; those who have a weak social personality and choose middle-level exit got the observed frequency of 1 with the expected frequency of 0.04; while those who have a very weak social personality and preferred middle-level as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and 0.29.

Lastly, those respondents who had a very strong social personality and chose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 9 and an expected frequency of 14.98; those who had a strong social personality and work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 5 and an expected frequency of 4.65; those who have a weak social personality got a null observed frequency and expected frequency of 0.17; those who are

very weak in terms of social personality got an observed frequency of 7 and an expected frequency of 1.20.

Notably, most of the respondents who choose college as their curriculum exit have a very strong and strong social personality. The decision to take the route of entrepreneurship, middle-skill development, and work is just an alternative route, and the influence of that decision is more on the side of those who are very strong and strong in terms of social personality. A social or helper personality type is a dedicated leader, humanistic, responsible, and supportive. They enjoy informing, helping, training, developing, and curing people in their work. Their empathy and sensitivity to emotional cues help them solve people’s problems, sometimes before others are aware of them. These individuals can pull people together and generate positive energy for a good cause.

Table 10. Correlation Between Enterprising Personality and Preferred Curriculum Exit

ENTERPRISING VS. CURRICULUM EXITS	HIGHLY EVIDENT		EVIDENT		RARELY EVIDENT		NOT EVIDENT		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Higher Education “Kolehiyo”	38	35.66	7	5.94	0	1.70	0	1.70	45
Middle-level Skills Devt. Employment “Trabaho”	0	0.79	0	0.13	1	0.04	0	0.04	1
Employment “Trabaho”	4	5.55	0	0.92	1	0.26	2	0.26	7
TOTAL	42		7		2		2		53
x^2 COMP=42.83 x^2 TAB=12.592 DF= 6 SIGNIFICANT 0.5 LEVEL									

Table 10 shows the Chi-Square correlation between the enterprising personality of the respondents and their preferred curriculum exits. It shows that those who have a very strong enterprising personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 38 and an expected frequency of 35.66; those who have a strong enterprising personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 7 and the expected frequency of 5.94; those who have a weak and very weak enterprising personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 1.70 respectively.

On the other hand, nobody among the respondents who has an enterprising personality has chosen entrepreneurship (Negosyo) as their curriculum exit.

While those respondents who had very strong, strong, and very weak enterprising personalities preferred Middle-level skills development exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.79, 0.13, and 0.04 respectively; while those who had a weak enterprising personality and chose middle-level skills development got the observed frequency of 1 and an observed frequency of 0.04.

Lastly, those who have a very strong enterprising personality and choose work (trabaho) as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 4 and an observed

frequency of 5.55; while those who have a strong enterprising personality and preferred work (Trabaho) exit got a null observed frequency and 0.92 expected frequency; those who have a weak enterprising personality and choose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 0.26; those who are very weak in terms of enterprising and choose work (trabaho) as their exit personality got an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 0.26.

Notably, most of the respondents who choose college as their curriculum exit have a very strong and strong enterprising personality. The decision to take the route of middle-skill development and work is just an alternative route and influential to that decision is more on the side of those who are very strong and strong in terms of enterprising personalities. Nobody among the respondents has chosen Entrepreneurship (Negosyo) as their curriculum exit.

The Enterprising or Persuader Personality types are those with the extraverted, observant, thinking, and prospecting personality traits. Entrepreneurs are full of passion and energy, complemented by a rational, if sometimes distracted mind. Inspiring, convincing, and colorful, they are natural group leaders, pulling everyone along the path less traveled, bringing life and excitement everywhere they go.

Table 11. Correlation Between Conventional Personality and Preferred Curriculum Exit

CONVENTIONAL VS. CURRICULUM EXITS	VERY STRONG		STRONG		WEAK		VERY WEAK		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Higher Education "Kolehiyo"	82	75.31	15	17.77	2	2.538	0	3.38	99
Entrepreneurship "Negosyo"	0	1.52	2	0.36	0	0.051	0	0.07	2
Middle-level Skills Development	0	0.76	1	0.18	0	0.026	0	0.03	1
Employment "Trabaho"	7	11.41	3	2.69	1	0.385	4	0.51	15
TOTAL	89		21		3		4		117
χ^2 TAB=16.919		χ^2 COMP=46.72		DF=9		SIGNIFICANT		0.05 LEVEL	

Table 11 reveals the Chi-Square correlation between the conventional personality of the respondents and their preferred curriculum exits. It shows that those who have a very strong conventional personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 82 and an expected frequency of 75.31; those who have a strong conventional personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 15 and the expected frequency of 17.77; those who have a weak conventional personality and choose college as their curriculum exit got the observed

frequency of 2 with the expected frequency of 2.53; while those who have very weak conventional personality and preferred college as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and 3.38 expected frequency.

On the other hand, those who have a very strong, weak, and very weak conventional personality and choose Entrepreneurship (Negosyo) as their curriculum exit got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 1.52, 0.05, and 0.07 respectively; while those who are strong conventional personality and their preferred curriculum exit is Negosyo got the observed frequency of 2 and the expected frequency of 0.36.

The same observations in the middle-level skills development exit where those who have a very strong, weak, and very weak conventional personality got a null observed frequency and an expected frequency of 0.76, 0.02, and 0.03 respectively; while those who are strong conventional personalities, and choose middle-level skills curriculum exit got the observed frequency of 1 and the expected frequency of 0.18.

Lastly, those who have a very strong conventional personality and choose work (trabaho) as their curriculum exit got an observed frequency of 7 and an observed frequency of 11.41; while those who have a strong conventional personality and preferred work (trabaho) exit got the observed frequency of 3 and an expected frequency of 2.69; those who have a weak conventional personality and choose work (trabaho) as their exit got an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 0.38; those who are very weak in terms of conventional and choose work (Trabaho) as their exit personality got an observed frequency of 4 and an expected frequency of .51.

Notably, most of the respondents who choose college as their curriculum exit have a very strong and strong conventional personality. The decision to take the route of entrepreneurship, middle-skill development, and work is just an alternative route, and influential to that decision is more on the side of those who are very strong and strong in terms of conventional personality.

The Conventional or Organizers Personality types are characterized by a preference for structure and organization and a strong focus and tradition and duty. People with this personality type are often drawn to careers in fields such as law, medicine, and government. And some of the most successful people in the world have a Conventional personality type.

5. What are the localized policy guidelines of PROJECT: TSERA E2E to enhance the SHS curriculum exit fair of Paliparan III SHS?

As a result of the study, **Project TSERA E2E** which stands for Technology Skills Education Review and Advancement- Enrolment to Employment will not only focus on employment but the **four curriculum exits** that are adapted and feasible not only during face-to-face learning but also during crises where the COVID-19 pandemic is present. Schools and Parents are expected to collaborate in the educational formation of the students and put the interest of the learners as well as guide them properly in choosing the right curriculum exits suited to their preferences and capabilities.

Further, Project TSERA E2E will serve as the school banner program, that will enhance the existing policy guidelines on the SHS Curriculum Exit Fair with meaningful

activities and programs that prepare students for the right choice and decision in “entering the exits for the SHS curriculum.

- 1. Higher Education (Kolehiyo)** – conduct Career Talk/Orientation/Caravan participated by both public and private Colleges and State Universities considering the existence of the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act, known as Republic Act 10931. Private institutions also have good scholastic and scholarship programs that can be offered to the students. The school may also process the application program for entrance exams in big universities within Cavite and Metro Manila.
 - 2. Employment (Trabaho)** – coordinate with DOLE for the conduct of Labor Education for Graduating Students (LEGS) and PESO for the Job Fair after their graduation so that the requirements or documents are ready for possible job placement. The Work Immersion Program can also be a good venue for some students to be absorbed after their graduation.
 - 3. Entrepreneurship (Negosyo)** – intensify the Entrepreneurship subject in the school so that the theory and dealing with business must be applied through a 3-day to 1-week Business Enterprise Simulation/Entrepreneurship Culminating Activity.
 - 4. Middle-Level Skills Development** – invite TESDA to present their scholarship programs including their NC II Assessment and Certification program. Likewise, TVET training centers like Dual Teach Training Center Foundation, Inc. and Iskolar ni Juan by Gokongwei Brother Foundation must be invited to present their TVET program, scholarship, and on-the-job training with allowance (minimum wages) leading to employment.
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Conclusions

1. The learner’s basic information shows that respondents were 502 students with 256 males and 246 females, they represent the number of respondents based on a stratified sub-group sample size. Mostly they belong to the 17-18 years old bracket with 356 learners and to poor families wherein 226 respondents declare that their average monthly family income is below P10,957.00.
2. Most respondents are social in terms of their personality types considering their residence location and environment.
3. A notable number of respondents wanted to take a college degree after graduation.
4. Based on the key findings, there is a significant correlation between the personality types of the respondents and their curriculum exits.
5. Project TSERA E2E v2.0 will serve as the school banner program, that will enhance the existing policy guidelines on the SHS Curriculum Exit Fair with meaningful activities and programs that prepare students for the right choice and decision in “entering the exits for the SHS curriculum.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussion as well as data analysis, the following recommendations are offered.

1. The Grade 12 Senior High School students are recommended to (a) Take a scientifically valid career test like the RIASEC that measures their personality types and identify those most likely to fit the careers or occupations they prefer; (b) Choose a career pathway specifically their preferred SHS curriculum exits that is suited to their prevalent personality types which are Social, Conventional, and Realistic.
2. The School Administrators and guidance teachers are expected to use the result of the study to make some necessary adjustments in the implementation of the DepEd Career Guidance Program by SY 2021-2022, (DM-OUCI-2021-346) known as Revised Implementation Homeroom Guidance (HG) during a crisis for SY 2021-2022 and succeeding years upon publication on the website as stated, the HGP Timeline shall be implemented for SY 2022-2023.
3. The Project: TSERA E2E Focal Person and Technical working group committee will implement the four SHS curriculum exits through programs, fairs, and activities that will guide the students in choosing the right curriculum exits before their graduation.
4. Further and similar studies may be conducted to substantiate the findings of the study. The research contains information that may be archived and can be used to compare future data.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The survey questionnaire was attached with an informed consent form where selected respondents were invited to participate in the study. They are asked to complete a few questions relevant to conducting the said study. Their answer will be kept confidential. In the records, the respondents' names will not be associated with their responses. Participation is voluntary, and they may withdraw from the survey at any time or decline to answer any questions that make them uncomfortable. In addition, they will take 3-5 minutes to candidly answer the items in the questionnaire. Respondents were given assurance that all answers will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be used for academic purposes only and that the information they have provided will be handled properly under the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2022.

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